

NDAC/LO/022

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WP7100: Back-Substitution (Definition)

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1. Principles

Having determined the orientation parameters (zero points) of each set by means of the PRS Solution (Step 2), the different abscissa measurements of a given star can be referred to a unique celestial coordinate system and its astrometric parameters calculated in that system. The name 'Back-Substitution' for this process is really motivated only for PRS stars, in that their astrometric parameters, previously eliminated from the PRS normals, are now obtained (formally) by substituting the PRS solution back into the eliminated equations.

However, as the class of stars designated PRS can be enlarged, successively and in the course of reductions, until practically all apparently 'single' stars are included, it is more convenient to regard the back-substitution for all programme stars as a natural part of the PRS solution, rather than as a separate and subsequent process. This point of view is further supported by the following observations:

- (i) The observation equations for the astrometric parameters are exactly identical to the corresponding part of the PRS equations and are available, in the PRS solution, in precisely the required order (viz., one star at a time).
- (ii) The PRS processing is of course iterative, producing a succession of eventually vanishing correction vectors. The back-solution of astrometric parameters is then actually replaced by a preadjustment of the same parameters before their elimination. The Step 3 residuals are available at this stage and can thus be used to decide, at the latest possible

time, whether the star should be included in the PRS solution or not. In the latter case, the process simply proceeds to the next star, without updating the PRS normals.

- (iii) By performing the slit error analysis (by the mesh method) in conjunction with the preadjustment mentioned above, it will be possible to get many more stars into the PRS solution, skipping only suspected double stars and those with ambiguous slit solutions.

The Back-Substitution then simply reduces to two sub-processes ('subroutines') in the PRS solution, viz.

MESH - solution of slit errors by the mesh method

ADJUST - preadjustment of astrometric parameters

The PRS solution takes as input the set results for all programme stars, sorted by star; but the PRS normals are accumulated only for a predefined category of stars successfully passing the MESH and ADJUST routines.

2. Summary of I/O Data

In consequence with the above principles, there is no separate data input to the Back-Substitution (but only via the PRS solution). The relevant Data Interface Descriptions are:

DID#	DESTINATION	DATA OUTPUT FROM BACK-SUBSTITUTION
37	Star Catalogue	• updated astrometric parameters, multiplicity indicator, etc
38	Double Stars	• residuals and coefficients of the astrometric parameters (complete Step 3 observation equations)

3. Method and Basic Equations

3.1. Preadjustment of astrometric parameters (ADJUST)

Details on the observation equation were given in NDAC/LO/021 (Definition of PRS Solution) and need not be repeated here.

For the observation of star i in set j we thus have

$$\underline{A}_{ij} \underline{\Delta a}_i + \underline{B}_{ij} \underline{\Delta b}_j + \underline{G}_{ij} \underline{\Delta g} + (\text{unit covariance noise}) = h_{ij} \quad (1)$$

with $\underline{a}_i$ containing the astrometric parameters, $\underline{b}_j$ the set orientation, and $\underline{g}$ the global distortion parameters. The right hand side is the normalized O-C,

$$h_{ij} = (\bar{v}_{ij \text{ obs}} - \bar{v}_{ij \text{ comp}}) / \sigma_{v_{ij}} \quad (2)$$

Iterating the PRS solution until the correction vectors $\underline{\Delta b}_j$ and $\underline{\Delta g}$ vanish, we have a simplified system of equations with normals

$$\left[\sum_j \underline{A}'_{ij} \underline{A}_{ij} \right] \underline{\Delta a}_i = \sum_j \underline{A}'_{ij} h_{ij} \quad (3)$$

⇔

$$\underline{P} \underline{\Delta a}_i = \underline{s} \quad (4)$$

where $\underline{P}$ is of dimension (NASPAR, NASPAR) [(5, 5) normally]. Solving (4) and updating $\underline{a}_i$ correspondingly implicitly assumes $\underline{\Delta b}_j = \underline{0}$ and $\underline{\Delta g} = \underline{0}$, which eventually becomes true (in the last PRS iteration). Doing this adjustment simultaneously with the elimination of $\underline{\Delta a}_i$ from the PRS normals, i.e. before solving $\underline{\Delta b}_j$, $\underline{\Delta g}$, makes it unnecessary to backsolve the astrometric parameters after the (final) PRS solution. Hence the name 'preadjustment'.

Equation (4) is solved in two steps after Cholesky decomposition of $\underline{P}$:

$$\underline{P} =: \underline{\tilde{P}}^T \underline{\tilde{P}} \quad (5)$$

$$\underline{\tilde{s}} = \underline{\tilde{P}}^{-T} \underline{s} \quad (6a)$$

$$\underline{\Delta a}_i = \underline{\tilde{P}}^{-1} \underline{\tilde{s}} \quad (6b)$$

which are explicit processes since $\underline{\tilde{P}}$ is triangular.

The preadjustment itself is an iterative process, in that the (O-C)s (h_{ij}) are recomputed after each updating of the astrometric parameters ($\underline{a}_i := \underline{a}_i + \underline{\Delta a}_i$). (The Cholesky factor $\underline{\tilde{P}}$ is however not updated in this iteration loop, but only in the outer loop of the PRS solution.) The iteration stops when the 'numerical noise' $|\underline{\tilde{s}}|$ is negligible compared with the observation noise (χ^2). The latter is computed as

$$\begin{aligned} \chi^2 &= \sum_j |h_{ij} - \underline{A}_{ij} \underline{\Delta a}_i|^2 \\ &= \sum_j \left[h_{ij}^2 - 2 \underline{\Delta a}_i' \underline{A}_{ij}' h_{ij} + \underline{\Delta a}_i' \underline{A}_{ij}' \underline{A}_{ij} \underline{\Delta a}_i \right] \\ &= \sum_j h_{ij}^2 - 2 \underline{\Delta a}_i' \underline{s} + \underline{\Delta a}_i' \underline{P} \underline{\Delta a}_i \\ &= \sum_j h_{ij}^2 - \underline{\tilde{s}}' \underline{\tilde{s}} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The logarithm of the ratio (obs noise)/(comp noise) is called 'numerical precision exponent',

$$\text{enp} = \frac{1}{2} \log_{10} (\chi^2 / \underline{\tilde{s}}' \underline{\tilde{s}}) \quad (8)$$

and should be at least ~ 3 for 'convergence'.

The subprocess ADJUST is outlined in Table 3. Note that $\underline{P}$ and $\underline{\tilde{P}}$ are computed outside the subprocess, while h_{ij} (for each set in which the star is included) must be recomputed as part of the preadjustment. The complete set of coefficients $\{\underline{A}_{ij} \quad \underline{B}_{ij} \dots\}_j$ for the star (i) must be available in primary memory throughout the i-loop of the PRS solution (cf Table 1).

3.2. Elimination of slit errors (MESH)

Slit errors occur because of phase ambiguity of the IDT signal for stars with inaccurate *a priori* positions. They are seen in the abscissa results $\bar{u}_{ij}$ as an error (in addition to the systematic orientation error and random observation error) being a small but unknown integer multiple of the average grid period. On the right-hand side of the normalised observation equation (2), the slit error is then a multiple of

$$k_{ij} = \langle \frac{\partial v}{\partial G} \rangle / \sigma_{v_{ij}} \quad (9)$$

with $\langle \rangle$ denoting an average over the different observations in set j of the star. From the Set Solution observation equation (001.1) we have

$$\frac{\partial G}{\partial v} = \sec \zeta \cos \rho [a \cos \epsilon - b \sin \epsilon] \quad (10)$$

From this and (001.3) - (001.5) we derive (assuming $\langle \eta \rangle = \langle \zeta \rangle = 0$ and $\langle \zeta^2 \rangle = \Phi_t^2/12$, with $\Phi_t =$ transversal FOV)

$$\langle \frac{\partial v}{\partial G} \rangle \approx \frac{1 - \Phi_t^2/24}{g_{10} \bar{r}'_j \bar{z}_{ij} - g_{01} \bar{r}'_j (\bar{z}_{ij} \wedge \bar{u}_{ij})} \quad (11)$$

in which $\bar{z}_{ij}$ is the mean direction of z for the observations of star i in set j . While $\bar{r}_j$ and $\bar{u}_{ij}$ are of course available when calculating the PRS observation coefficients, this is not the case with $\bar{z}_{ij}$. It could be computed from attitude data at the mean time of observation ($\bar{t}_{ij}$), but it is of course much better to calculate the average $\partial v / \partial G$ directly in the Set Solution, since the coefficients (10) of each frame observation are anyhow needed there.

The mesh method for eliminating slit errors is described by Høg and Poder (1982 Nov 12) and Lindegren (1983 Jan 31), and has been tested successfully by Kjaergaard-Andreasen (report in progress). The basic idea is to try a number of different

starting approximations $\delta_{\underline{a}_m}$, constituting a dense mesh ($m = 1$ to M) over the region of *a priori* uncertainty. For each mesh point the observation equations for the correction vector $\Delta_{\underline{a}_1}$ are

$$\underline{A}_{ij} \Delta_{\underline{a}_1} + (\text{unit covariance noise}) = h_{ij} + K_j k_{ij} \quad (12)$$

in which the integers K_j are chosen to make the residuals with respect to the mesh point all absolutely less than half a grid period:

$$|h_{ij} + K_j k_{ij} - \underline{A}_{ij} \delta_{\underline{a}_m}| < \frac{1}{2} k_{ij} \quad (13)$$

The equations (12) are solved as in Section 3.1 and the sum-square of residuals, χ^2 , computed. The solution yielding the smallest χ^2 is normally adopted. (Usually more than one starting approximation will converge to the same $\Delta_{\underline{a}_1}$ and χ^2 .)

The *a priori* knowledge of the astrometric parameters may be incorporated in the search process by limiting the mesh to a certain volume of the NASPAR-dimensional space e.g. within 3σ of the *a priori* vector ($\Delta_{\underline{a}_1} = \underline{0}$); or (better?) by means of a quadratic loss function $|\underline{L}\Delta_{\underline{a}_1}|^2$ increasing with the 'normalised' distance of the solution from the *a priori* vector. The loss matrix $\underline{L}$ is typically diagonal and containing the inverse *a priori* mean errors (very conservative estimates must be used!). I emphasise that this loss function is introduced purely in order to restrict the search volume in a smooth way; it must not be used in the final adjustment of the astrometric parameters. (As a general principle the final HIPPARCOS results should be independent of any *a priori* information about the astrometric parameters, apart from the global system orientation and rotation.)

A solution of the slit ambiguity problem has been found if the smallest χ^2 falls below a preset limit depending on the number of sets (observation equations). In the MESH algorithm outlined in Table 2, this condition is indicated by setting a logical variable find := true. As shown by the simulations

by Kjaergaard-Andreasen, this is however not always sufficient to guarantee that the solution is true (i.e. that the correct set of integers K_j has been found). Indeed, if the algorithm is applied after only 6 or 12 months of observation, the probability is quite significant that a false position is found, corresponding to another intersection of the 'probability ridges' associated with each scan. In that case, however, the next smallest χ^2 (which may correspond to the correct solution) is usually only slightly larger, so that the difference $\Delta\chi^2$ can be taken as an indicator of the 'uniqueness' of the solution. In the MESH algorithm, a logical variable ambiguous := true if $\Delta\chi^2$ is less than a certain limit.

Failure of convergence (find = false) is an indication of multiplicity and the entire system of observation equations (12) is then saved for the double star analysis.

A doubtful solution (ambiguous = true) will lead to updating of the astrometric parameters (in ADJUST), but the results are flagged.

A star is used in the PRS solution only if the MESH solution has converged (find = true) to a unique result (ambiguous = false), and the star belongs to a predefined subset (prs = true).

3.3. Place in PRS solution

The inclusion of MESH and ADJUST in the PRS solution has been outlined in Table 1, which replaces Table 1 in NDAC/LO/021. The previous scheme actually contains two errors, which have been corrected in the present Table 1: firstly, a matrix $Q = \sum_j A'_{ij} B_{ij}$ was accumulated and reduced, although it is not needed anywhere; secondly, the accumulation of $-(R \underline{g})'(R \underline{g})$ should take place outside the j-loop 2.5 and not in 2.5.2. The new scheme also indicates where blunder detection could take place ($|h_{ij}| > \text{lim}_1$) and takes advantage of that $\sum_j A'_{ij} h_{ij} = 0$ as a result of the preadjustment, which simplifies the calculation of right-hand sides of the PRS normals. For better clarity, a tilde ($\sim$) is now used for matrices which have been Cholesky reduced, i.e. premultiplied by $\tilde{P}^{-T}$.

TABLE 1. Accumulation of PRS normals with elimination of slit errors, MESH, and preadjustment of astrometric parameters, ADJAST

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zero all  $\underline{D}_{jj}$ ,  $\underline{E}_j$ ,  $\underline{e}_j$  and  $\underline{F}$ ,  $\underline{f}$ 
loop through stars i
  if (i belongs to preselected PRS) then (prs := true)
    ( $\underline{P}$   $\underline{R}$ ) :=  $\underline{0}$ (NASPAR, NASPAR+NGBLOB)
    n := 0,  $\chi_0^2 := 0$ 
    loop through sets j
      compute ( $\underline{A}_{ij}$   $\underline{B}_{ij}$   $\underline{G}_{ij}$   $h_{ij}$   $k_{ij}$ )
      if ( $|h_{ij}| > \text{lim}_1$ ) then (reduce observation weight)
       $\underline{H}_j := \underline{A}_{ij}' \underline{B}_{ij}$ 
      ( $\underline{P}$   $\underline{R}$ ) := ( $\underline{P}$   $\underline{R}$ ) +  $\underline{A}_{ij}' (\underline{A}_{ij} \underline{G}_{ij})$ 
      n := n + 1,  $\chi_0^2 := \chi_0^2 + h_{ij}^2$ 
    next j
    if ( $\underline{P} > \underline{0}$ ) then
      ( $\tilde{\underline{P}}$   $\tilde{\underline{R}}$ ) :=  $\tilde{\underline{P}}^{-T} (\underline{P} \underline{R})$  [Cholesky reduction]
      call MESH
      if (find = true) then (call ADJAST)
      if (prs = true) and (find = true) and (ambiguous = false) then
        loop through sets j
           $\tilde{\underline{H}}_j := \tilde{\underline{P}}^{-T} \underline{H}_j$ 
          loop through sets  $j < j$ :  $\underline{D}_{jj} := \underline{D}_{jj} - \tilde{\underline{H}}_j' \tilde{\underline{H}}_j$ 
          ( $\underline{D}_{jj}$   $\underline{E}_j$   $\underline{e}_j$ ) := ( $\underline{D}_{jj}$   $\underline{E}_j$   $\underline{e}_j$ ) +  $\underline{B}_{ij}' (\underline{B}_{ij} \underline{G}_{ij} h_{ij}) - \tilde{\underline{H}}_j' (\tilde{\underline{H}}_j \tilde{\underline{R}} \underline{0})$ 
          ( $\underline{F}$   $\underline{f}$ ) := ( $\underline{F}$   $\underline{f}$ ) +  $\underline{G}_{ij}' (\underline{G}_{ij} h_{ij})$ 
        next j
         $\underline{F} := \underline{F} - \tilde{\underline{R}}' \tilde{\underline{R}}$ 
      endif
    endif
  endif
next i

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TABLE 2. Elimination of slit errors (MESH)

input: $\{A_{ij}, h_{ij}, k_{ij}\}_j, \tilde{P}, n, \chi_0^2$, (*a priori* astrometric covariance)

find := false, ambiguous := true

define mesh size M and loss matrix $\underline{L}$ (depending on *a priori* covariance)

loop through mesh m := 1 to M

 define mesh point $\underline{da}_m$

$\underline{s} := \underline{0}(\text{NASPAR}, 1)$

 loop through sets j

$r := h_{ij} + k_{ij} * \text{NINT}[(A_{ij} \underline{da}_m - h_{ij}) / k_{ij}]$

$\underline{s} := \underline{s} + A_{ij}' r$

 next j

$\tilde{\underline{s}} := \tilde{P}^{-T} \underline{s}$

$\underline{da}_m := \tilde{P}^{-1} \tilde{\underline{s}}$

$\chi_m^2 := \chi_0^2 - \tilde{\underline{s}}' \tilde{\underline{s}} + (\underline{L} \underline{da}_m)' (\underline{L} \underline{da}_m)$

 compare $\underline{da}_m$ with previous solutions and rank according to χ_m^2 , thus creating a list $\{m1, m2, \dots\}$ with distinct $\underline{da}_{mr}$ and $\chi_{m1}^2 \leq \chi_{m2}^2 \leq \dots$

next m

if [$\chi_{m1}^2 < \text{lim}_2(n)$] then

$\underline{da}_i := \underline{da}_m$

$\chi^2 := \chi_{m1}^2$

 find := true

endif

if [$(\chi_{m2}^2 - \chi_{m1}^2) < \text{lim}_3(n)$] then (ambiguous := true)

output: find, ambiguous, $\underline{da}_i, \chi^2$

TABLE 3. Preadjustment of astrometric parameters (ADJUST)

input: $\underline{a}_i, \Delta \underline{a}_i, \{A_{ij}\}_j, \tilde{\underline{P}}$

enp := 0

while (enp < lim₄) do

$\underline{a}_i := \underline{a}_i + \Delta \underline{a}_i$

$\underline{s} := 0(\text{NASPAR}, 1)$

$\chi_0^2 := 0$

 loop through sets j

 recompute h_{ij} using updated $\underline{a}_i$

$\underline{s} := \underline{s} + A'_{ij} h_{ij}$

$\chi_0^2 := \chi_0^2 + h_{ij}^2$

 next j

$\tilde{\underline{s}} := \tilde{\underline{P}}^{-T} \underline{s}$

$\chi^2 := \chi_0^2 - \tilde{\underline{s}}' \tilde{\underline{s}}$

$\Delta \underline{a}_i := \tilde{\underline{P}}^{-1} \tilde{\underline{s}}$

 enp := $\frac{1}{2} \log_{10} (\chi^2 / \tilde{\underline{s}}' \tilde{\underline{s}})$

repeat

$\underline{a}_i := \underline{a}_i + \Delta \underline{a}_i$

output: $\underline{a}_i, \{h_{ij}\}_j, \chi^2$

DID 37		OUTPUT FROM : BACK-SUBSTITUTION				PAGE : 1 OF 1		
INPUT TO : STAR CATALOGUE		RANGE		NUM ACC		DIG-		
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	MAX	ABS	REL	ITS
ID	-	1. For each star: object identification number	-	0	$9 \cdot 10^8$	1	-	8
RA $\emptyset$	α_o (p4)	(updated) RA at TEPOCH	rad	$-\pi$	π	10^{-11}	-	12
DEC $\emptyset$	δ_o (p4)	(updated) Dec at TEPOCH	rad	$-\frac{1}{2}\pi$	$\frac{1}{2}\pi$	10^{-11}	-	12
PMRA	$\mu_\alpha \cos \delta_o$	(updated) p.m. in RA at TEPOCH	rad/s	-10^{-11}	10^{-11}	10^{-19}	-	9
PMDEC	μ_δ (p4)	(updated) p.m. in Dec at TEPOCH	rad/s	-10^{-11}	10^{-11}	10^{-19}	-	9
PX	$\tilde{\omega}$ (p4)	(updated) trigonometric parallax	rad	$-5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	10^{-11}	-	6
MULT	-	(updated) multiplicity information	-	0	9999	1	-	4
NOBS	-	number of abscissa observations	-	0	999	1	-	3
GOF3	χ^2 (p37)	Step 3 goodness-of-fit	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	10^{-6}	6
COVAST(K,L), K=1,5; L=1,K	-	covariance of updated astrometric parameters	-	-10^{38}	10^{38}	-	10^{-6}	6
ISET	j (p35)	1.1. For each abscissa observation (set): set identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^5$	1	-	6
TOBS	$t_o + \tau$ (p4)	mean time of observation ($\bar{t}_{ij}$)	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	10^{-6}	-	15
RES3	$\Delta T_j - \Delta T_j^i$ $j^i_{(p37)}$	abscissa residual	rad	-10^{-5}	10^{-5}	10^{-11}	-	7
SDABSC	σ_{ji} (p37)	standard deviation of abscissa	rad	-10^{-5}	10^{-5}	10^{-11}	-	7
WEIGHT	-	weight factor (normally = 1)	-	0	10	-	10^{-6}	6

DID 38		OUTPUT FROM : BACK-SUBSTITUTION INPUT TO : DOUBLE STARS				PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 83.07.05			
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL	DIG- ITS
ID	-	1. <u>For each suspected multiple star:</u> object identification number	-	0	9.10 ⁸	0	1	-	8
NOBS	-	number of abscissa observations	-	0	999	0	1	-	3
ISET	j (p35)	1.1. <u>For each abscissa observation (set):</u> set identification number	-	1	9.10 ⁵	-	1	-	6
TOBS	t _o +t (p4)	mean time of observation ($\bar{T}_{ij}$)	s	0	2.10 ⁸	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	15
RES3	$\Delta T_{ji} - \Delta T_{ji}^{\wedge}$	abscissa residual (p37)	rad	-10 ⁻⁵	10 ⁻⁵	0	10 ⁻¹¹	-	7
SDABSC	σ_{ji} (p37)	standard deviation of abscissa	rad	-10 ⁻⁵	10 ⁻⁵	0	10 ⁻¹¹	-	7
WEIGHT	-	weight factor (normally = 1)	-	0	10	1	-	10 ⁻⁶	6
ACOEFF(K), K=1,5	-	coefficient matrix for astrometric parameters (A_{ij})	-	-10 ³⁸	10 ³⁸	0	-	10 ⁻⁶	6
ABSCPG	-	abscissa per grid period $\langle \partial u / \partial G \rangle_{ij}$	rad	0	10 ⁻⁵	-	10 ⁻¹¹	-	7